

COMPUTER INTERACTION WITH STUDENTS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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***Annotation.** This article describes the design of lessons based on the use of Internet technologies in language teaching, the acquisition of knowledge by students, the further strengthening of knowledge, independent thinking and worldview, modern knowledge and thinking and, most importantly, the study of correct and fluent language. It is thought that the computer system assists in the assimilation of certain types of information.*

***Key words.** interactive, e-mail, information technology, computer literacy, e-learning, dialogue, video, graphic organizers.*

The use of information technology in education is one of the most important issues for all science teachers today. In particular, the help of computer systems in the acquisition of knowledge, in the acquisition of certain types of information is enormous. "The task of teaching children and young people special sciences, the history of our country and world civilization, foreign languages and modern computer programs has not yet been fully and qualitatively solved." ¹That is why the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation is the main task of our state. In particular, if we emphasize the computer-related tasks of Uzbek linguistics, they include: the creation of a computer style of the Uzbek language, standardization of information texts, standards of brevity development, setting standards for creating websites, creating computer annotated and translated dictionaries, developing electronic versions of textbooks of Uzbek language and literature, developing

¹ Sh.Mirziyoev. Critical analysis, strict discipline - and personal responsibility - should be a daily rule of every leader. Tashkent - "Uzbekistan", 2017, p. 49.

English-Uzbek translation programs on the computer, creating programs for automatic editing of computer texts.

As a result, the need for the Internet is growing among linguists, especially in today's online learning environment.

Because information technology, especially the Internet, develops students' intellectual and critical thinking skills. It is possible to provide them with a certain amount of additional material via the Internet.

It is important that the use of Internet technology in the learning process should be fully controlled by the teacher. In this process, the following requirements are set for teachers:²

- 1) knowledge of computer literacy and use of Internet technologies;
- 2) organization of students' activities related to the search and analysis of necessary materials;
- 3) such as monitoring the stages of students' work on the Internet and assessing its quality.

One of the tasks in ensuring the effectiveness of the use of information technology is the methodological development of pedagogical technologies. The organization of group and individual forms of work of students on the Internet has a special didactic value. It is advisable to organize the following activities in the process of learning new materials on the Internet with an individual approach to students:

- Explain the materials by the teacher to all students in the group;
- Divide students into groups based on their abilities;
 - give creative assignments to group members;
 - selection of leading methods and ways of work for each member of the group;

² A.T.Baltaeva. Technology to teach students to critically evaluate the heroes of a work of art in literature classes. Ped. fan. Ph.D. (PhD) diss. T., 2020. - 140 p.

- summarizing the results on the basis of tasks and final work;
- evaluation of the results of the group members on the basis of the analysis.

There are several types of innovative educational technologies available today. When they are used extensively and in a variety of ways to cover a topic in the classroom, the effectiveness of the lesson is high and the interest of the students in the lesson is increased. It is intended to increase the effectiveness of education through the introduction and implementation of innovations in the educational process. The use of different roles and movement games in the teaching of Uzbek and Russian language classes will increase the interest in language learning in the classroom. Students work in pairs or small groups to help them communicate with others. The use of graphic organizers is one of the most important tools in illuminating a topic and delivering it to students. It is also possible to use several different graphic organizers to illuminate a theme. It is a good idea to use graphic organizers to explain new words and grammar rules. These can be easily memorized by graphic organizers. The use of different tables in teaching Uzbek, Russian, English and other languages is also very effective. In the learning process, using tables, students can follow a specific grammatical rule, such as composing sentences using tenses and placing new words. At a time when there is a high need for language learning, the effective use of modern information technologies, innovative educational technologies in the educational process makes this process more effective.

Especially in Uzbek language classes, each stage of text study has its own goals and objectives. Materials are selected and mastered in connection with the same goals and objectives. Or the study of the biographies of writers is directly related to the literary journey. Such a journey, in turn, should be associated with the life and work of the writer. Pictures of the author himself, family members, contemporaries, friends, colleagues give the necessary information about the environment in which he lived and worked. In this process, students can quickly

achieve the expected results if they have the opportunity to take a look at the writer's creative lab and listen to parts of the text performed by art reading masters. Reading a piece to the sound of music requires choosing music that is close to his soul.

It is also important to take advantage of nearby art forms when studying texts. Examples include fine arts, music, theater, and performing arts. Excerpts from the artwork should be read or shown during the presentation. Illustrations, paintings, miniatures, theatrical scenes, screenplays, and musicals that were close to the subject served to vividly embody the characters' actions and characteristics. The use of additional illustrations during the presentation, the study of the work of art by students, and the critical assessment of its protagonists were of particular interest. Their level of mastery of the learning materials increased and their attention span stabilized. Slide-based presentation technology does not take the teacher away from the learning process. The main audio part of the lectures is the teacher's own voice, which interprets the slides, forms definitions, and controls the rhythm of the lectures and the exchange of slides.

Most students are well versed in the Internet. That is why the group work method is used. The potential of this type of information technology is of particular interest to students, who analyze the texts using Internet materials and make a presentation of the content of the text, and the teacher selects the materials necessary to reveal the content of the text - the character . , can prepare their presentation using slides and give assignments on how to defend it. The teacher selects the materials that students need to reveal the character of the text. This will take 15-20 minutes. Given the use of group work, there will be enough time to monitor and evaluate the performance of this work. Students will develop a positive attitude towards new material. Their level of independence will increase, and a healthy competitive environment will be created. Students analyze the presented texts on the basis of slides and make a presentation. As they prepare the slides, they re-learn the pronunciation of many words. In particular, the preparation of dictionaries on the

topic in the form of presentations will save time. In addition, there will be an opportunity to communicate with speakers of different languages via the Internet. Thus, the need to expand the use of illustrative materials is identified. The role of the teacher as a mentor is especially important here.

The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology can help you learn languages, such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking. For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CD. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time.

When using computers, students can watch and listen to Uzbek-language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons, listen to and watch radio and television programs. CD players can also use tape recorders and cassettes. The use of these techniques makes the process of learning languages more interesting and effective for students.

Recommendations for the use of Internet resources will also be developed during the organization of lessons. It includes links and quotes to make the job easier. The file is placed in a special folder. Students will refer to these materials one by one. The list was completed by the students themselves during the school year.

Virtual trips to the writers' home museums during the course are also effective. They will be able to see with their own eyes the places and landscapes that they have learned through literary works. They have a special interest in this type of work and will have the opportunity to refer to the work and get acquainted with the views of the writer's contemporaries.

It is advisable to use the Internet, especially when performing text analysis in the process of independent work. The Internet can also be used effectively to find and identify the means of expression, the places that describe the participants in a

text. In addition, dictionaries posted on websites increase the vocabulary of readers and make it easier to find the words and phrases needed to describe the characters of the work, their meanings.

The following types of work can be taught online using stylistic analysis of the text. In this process, the teacher works according to a pre-prepared plan. After reviewing this example, learners demonstrate stylistic units that distinguish them from the text.

E-mails can serve the same purpose. Thinking about and evaluating the heroes mentioned in the text via email is also a somewhat promising type of activity. This can help learners develop the ability to write descriptions. The wide range of e-mails allows your teammates to write reviews of what they have read. It is also possible to improve the practice of writing letters through other channels via e-mail. In doing so, the student should, as far as possible, try to spell the words correctly according to the rules of spelling.

Psychologists have repeatedly said that the opinions of their peers are more important to students than the teacher. That's why groups send their texts to each other in writing to find out their peers' assessments of the objectivity of their opinions. This type of work develops students' responsibility, independence, critical thinking, tolerance and cooperation. The teacher monitors the process and evaluates the students' work. Many of the works have been read by art readers and posted on websites. These interactive portals include versions of works of art read by authors and actors. The use of online materials in the classroom is also convenient for teachers. There are also controversial posts on the Internet, which can be used selectively by comparing them with the originals.

Thus, the use of information technology allows for a person-centered approach to education.

When using information technology:

- the use of information technology to tell a story about themselves, to give others the opportunity to evaluate themselves;

- striving for originality;
- Satisfaction of curiosity;
- to be demanding of oneself.

This allows students to express themselves. practical experience shows that information technology and multimedia tools create a unique convenience.

In conclusion, interactive online teaching methods in Uzbek, Russian, English and language classes help to increase the huge educational potential of students, instill a competitive spirit in the learning process and intensify lessons. The interaction of learners and Internet technologies allows for the effective organization of lessons, diligent study of world languages, the formation of worldviews, in-depth knowledge.

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